

INVESTIGATION OF IQ-SPECTRA IN THE RECYCLING OF SECONDARY POLYVINYL CHLORIDE

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Abstract. The article presents the results of research on the IQ-spectra of secondary polyvinyl chloride waste. In order to plasticize secondary polyvinyl chloride waste, a 1:1 mixture of soap stock and dioctyl phthalate was used as a plasticizer.

Keywords: polyvinyl chloride, IQ-spectrum, soapstock, dioctylphthalate, aromatic ring, asymmetric, symmetric, polymer macromolecule.

INTRODUCTION

In the research conducted on the investigation of the IQ-spectra of secondary polyvinyl chloride (PVC) waste, in order to plasticize secondary polyvinyl chloride waste, a 1:1 mixture of waste soapstock from the local oil industry and dioctyl phthalate was used as a plasticizer.

Below are the results of the research conducted on the study of IQ-spectra of secondary PVC waste.

In doing so, we first obtained the IQ-spectra of secondary polyvinyl chloride and the IQ-spectra of soapstock. After that, we mixed the soap stock in different proportions of the secondary sample and obtained the IQ-spectra of the resulting samples.

Experiment 1. First, the infrared spectrum of the secondary PVC sample for research was studied in the spectrophotometer "Spekord-75UR" at a wavelength of 500-4000 cm⁻¹.

Figure 1. IQ-spectrum of secondary polyvinyl chloride.

The results are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Characteristic frequencies related to important groups in the IQ-spectrum of secondary polyvinyl chloride

The nature of vibration	Frequency, cm ⁻¹	Intensity
$\nu_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{as}}$	2914,44	strong
$\nu_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{s}}$	2846,93	strong
$\delta_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{s}}$	1462,04	average
δ_{CH}	1435,04	average
$\nu_{\text{C-C}}$	873,75	average
$\nu_{\text{C-Cl}}$	719,45	average

First, the IR-spectrum of secondary PVC was obtained for conducting research and comparison. This Table 1 gives the values of asymmetric and symmetric valence vibrations specific to CH₂, CH, C-C, C-Cl groups in secondary PVC.

Experiment 2. Then the infrared spectrum of the soapstock sample in Figure 2 was obtained:

Figure 2. IQ-spectrum of soapstock

Table 2

Characteristic frequencies of soapstock belonging to important groups in the IQ-spectrum

The nature of vibration	Frequency, cm ⁻¹	Intensity
ν_{OH} (connected)	3371,57	strong, average
$\nu_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{as}}$	2922,16	Strong
$\nu_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{s}}$	2852,72	strong, average
$\nu_{\text{C=C}}$	1645,28	average, weak
$\nu_{\text{C=C}}$ (double bond in an aromatic ring)	1548,84	average, weak
δ_{CH} (aromatic)	1463,97	average, weak
δ_{OH}	1406,11	Average
$\nu_{\text{CO}}^{\text{as}}$ (-C-O-H)	1085,99	average, weak
$\nu_{\text{CO}}^{\text{s}}$ (-C-O-H)	1053,13	average, weak
δ_{CH} (alkene)	993,34	Weak

In experiment 2, the IQ-spectrum of soapstock was obtained. This Table 2 shows the asymmetric and symmetric valence characteristic of CH₂, CH (aromatic), CH (alkene), C=C, CO, C=C (double bond in aromatic ring), OH (bonded) groups and other groups in soapstock values of fluctuations are given.

Experiment 3. Infrared spectra of samples of soapstock with secondary PVC in 1:0.1, 1:0.3 and 1:0.5 mass units were obtained in the following figures 3.4.3, 3.4.4, 3.4.5:

Figure 3. PVC+soapstock (0.1 m.b.) IQ-spectrum

Figure 4. PVC+soapstock (0.3 m.b.) IQ-spectrum

Figure 5. PVC+soapstock (0.5 m.p.) IQ-spectrum

Table 3

Characteristic frequencies related to important groups in IQ spectra of secondary PVC+soapstock (0.1, 0.3 and 0.5 m.p.)

The nature of vibration	Frequency, cm ⁻¹	Intensity
PVX $\nu_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{as}}$	2918,30	Strong
PVX $\nu_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{s}}$	2848,86	Strong
Soapstock $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$	1741,72	Weak
Soapstock $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ (double bond in an aromatic ring)	1558,48	Weak
PVX $\delta_{\text{CH}_2}^{\text{s}}$	1462,04	Average
PVX δ_{CH}	1444,68	Average
Soapstok δ_{OH}	1423,47	Average
Soapstock $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{H}}^{\text{as}}$ (-C-O-H) for the group	1109,07	Weak
Soapstock $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{H}}^{\text{s}}$ (-C-O-H) for the group	1053,13	Weak
Soapstock δ_{CH} (alkene)	923,90	Weak
PVX $\gamma_{\text{C}-\text{C}}$	873,75	Weak
PVX $\gamma_{\text{C}-\text{Cl}}$	719,45	average, weak
Soapstock $\delta_{=\text{CH}}$	698,23	average, weak

The values of asymmetric and symmetric valence vibrations specific to the CH₂ group in PVC ($n\text{CH}_2^{\text{as}}$) are 2914.44 cm⁻¹ to 2918.30 cm⁻¹ when soapstock is mixed with secondary PVC in ratios of 1:0.1, 1:0.3, and 1:0.5. ga, and it can be seen that the symmetric vibrations ($n\text{CH}_2^{\text{s}}$) have shifted slightly from 1846.93 cm⁻¹ to 2848.86 cm⁻¹. Similarly, the specific valence vibration of the C=C double bond in soapstock ($n\text{C}=\text{C}$) ranges from 1645.28 cm⁻¹ to 1741.72 cm⁻¹ and the

valence vibration of the aromatic ring specific double bond $nC=C$ (aromatic double bond in the ring) shifts bathochromically from 1548.84 cm^{-1} to 1558.48 cm^{-1} .

CONCLUSION

Based on the above experimental results, it can be concluded that the main reason for the improvement of the physical and mechanical properties of polymer macromolecules during the processing of plasticized (1:0.3 m.p.) secondary PVC composite mixtures is that the soapstock and DOF molecules are complete with polymer macromolecules. Mixture and the formation of dipole-dipole, electrostatic, hydrogen bond and physical effects can be seen from the changes in the peaks in the above spectra. Secondary PVC mixture with soapstock and DOF 1:0.3 m.b. obtained is an optimal working recipe, which can be used for the production and use of various plasticized polymer composite products for technical purposes.

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